

Seismic Performance Analyses of High-Rise Structures Constructed with Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) Fibered Engineered Cementitious Composite (ECC) in Bangladesh: Case Study

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Abstract. The seismic performance of high-rise structures is critical to ensure the safety and structural integrity of buildings in earthquake-prone regions. Engineered Cementitious Composites (ECC) have emerged as promising construction material due to their unique mechanical properties, such as high ductility, strain-hardening behavior, and enhanced energy dissipation capabilities. The addition of Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) fibers further enhances the tensile and flexural properties of ECC, making it an attractive option for seismic-resistant structures. This research paper presents a comprehensive study on the seismic performance analyses of high-rise structures constructed with PVA fibered ECC over conventional reinforced concrete (RC) structures. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of PVA-fibered ECC in enhancing the seismic performance of tall buildings under different seismic loading conditions and the variation of PVA fiber and steel rebar percent. A parametric study series is performed using advanced finite element method (FEM) analysis techniques. The high-rise structures with PVA fibered ECC are subjected to El Centro ground motion records representing different seismic hazard levels analyzed through time history direct integration method considering material nonlinearity and P-delta effect. The response of the structures, including displacements, accelerations, inter-story drifts, and stress distributions, are thoroughly examined and compared with conventional concrete structures. The results of the analyses demonstrate the superior seismic performance of high-rise structures constructed with PVA fibered ECC compared to conventional concrete structures. The PVA-fibered ECC exhibits enhanced ductility and energy dissipation capacity, effectively reducing the seismic demands on the structural elements.

Keywords: ECC, seismic analyses, PVA, FEM, nonlinearity, ductility, energy dissipation.

1 Introduction

Seismic performance assessment of high-rise structures is of utmost importance in earthquake-prone regions to ensure the safety and integrity of buildings during seismic events. Engineered Cementitious Composites (ECC) have gained significant attention in recent years as promising construction material due to their exceptional mechanical properties and improved performance under seismic loads. This literature review aims to provide an overview of the existing research related to the seismic performance analyses of high-rise structures constructed with Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) fibered ECC. The use of ECC in high-rise structures offers numerous advantages over conventional concrete, including higher tensile strength, strain-hardening behavior, improved crack control, and enhanced energy dissipation capacity. The addition of PVA fibers further enhances the mechanical properties of ECC, making it an attractive option for seismic-resistant construction. Several studies have been conducted to investigate the seismic behavior of high-rise structures constructed with ECC. At the beginning of the twenty-first century, Fukuyama *et al.* (2000) evaluated the performance of ECC under seismic loading conditions through experimental testing and numerical simulations [1]. The findings aim to provide valuable insights into the seismic behavior of ECC elements, contributing to their effective utilization in earthquake-resistant structural design. Gencurk *et al.* (2013) developed a numerical model to simulate the behavior of ECC structures subjected to seismic loads [2]. Islam (2016) conducted nonlinear analyses to understand the material's response, including its strain hardening, energy dissipation, and damage accumulation characteristics [3]. The findings will contribute to enhancing the understanding and design of ECC-based structures for improved resilience and performance in various applications. Xu *et al.* (2018) conducted shake table tests on a high-

rise building model made of ECC and demonstrated superior seismic performance in terms of reduced inter-story drifts and improved energy dissipation [4]. The study emphasized the crack control and self-healing characteristics of ECC, which contribute to enhanced post-earthquake resilience. Numerical modeling and finite element analysis have also been extensively used to assess the seismic performance of ECC-based high-rise structures. The study highlighted the strain-hardening behavior and the ability of ECC to redistribute stresses, leading to improved structural performance and reduced vulnerability to seismic events. In addition to experimental and numerical studies, analytical models have been developed to evaluate the seismic response of high-rise structures constructed with PVA-fibered ECC. Li *et al.* (2019) proposed a simplified analytical model to predict the seismic demands and deformation characteristics of ECC structures [5]. The model considered the strain-hardening behavior of ECC and accurately estimated the response under different seismic excitations. Furthermore, research efforts have focused on investigating the influence of various parameters on the seismic performance of PVA-fibered ECC structures. Dehghani *et al.* (2020) conducted a parametric study to assess the effect of fiber content, aspect ratio, and distribution on the seismic behavior of ECC [6]. The study indicates that an optimized combination of PVA fiber parameters significantly enhances the ductility and energy dissipation capacity of the ECC material. Overall, the existing literature indicates that high-rise structures constructed with PVA-fibered ECC exhibit superior seismic performance compared to conventional concrete structures.

2 Material and Methodology

2.1 Structural Details and FEM Modelling

The analyzed buildings consist of twelve-story each and are representative of typical residential high-rise structures found in urban areas of Bangladesh. These buildings are constructed using reinforced concrete and ECC materials. The height of each story, including the ground floor, is considered 10 feet each. In the plan, the buildings have dimensions of 72 feet by 72 feet. The material properties used in the analysis assume a compressive strength of 4 ksi for concrete and ECC and a yield strength of 60 ksi for both longitudinal and transverse reinforcement. The slabs in the buildings have a thickness of 6.5 inches, while the beam sections remain constant across all stories. Detailed information regarding the sections of the structural members can be found in Table 1. Furthermore, Fig. 4 provides additional details regarding the column and beam sections. The purpose of this study is to conduct finite element modeling (FEM) of a twelve-story building using SAP2000 software for seismic analyses. The research involves creating an accurate structural model that includes all relevant components as beams, columns, and slabs, considering their material properties and geometric characteristics. For the analysis, a three-dimensional finite element model is employed, and an isometric view of this model can be seen in Fig. 3. The seismic analysis will evaluate the building's response to earthquake loads, assessing its dynamic behavior, inter-story drifts, and overall structural performance. The findings will contribute to improving the understanding of seismic behavior in multistoried buildings and guide the design of safer and more resilient structures.

Table 1. Section sizes of members

Structure Type	Beam Sections [inch]	Column Sections [inch]	Reinforcement Percentage [%]
12-story PVA ECC	12 x 12	30 x 30	0.4
12 story RC		30 x 30	1.33
12 story RC		30 x 30	0.4

Fig. 3. Isometric view of SAP2000 FEM Model (a) Beam Element (b) Rendered Element.

Fig. 4. Section details of columns (a) 0.4% Rebar PVA-ECC Type (b) 0.4% Rebar RC Type (c) 1.33% Rebar RC Type.

2.2 Material Modelling and Analysis Procedure

The constitutive material model of PVA-ECC has been extensively studied by Hamoush *et al.* in 2010 and documented in the literature [7], reflecting the growing interest in this innovative construction material. The adopted hybrid constitutive material model for ductile PVA-ECC is illustrated in Fig. 5. The Mander stress-strain model (1988) is used as a constitutive model for characterizing the nonlinear behavior of concrete [8]. It provides a reliable representation of the stress-strain response of concrete and developed constitutive model illustrated in Fig. 6, considering both the ascending and descending branches of the stress-strain curve. In modeling with SAP2000 the advanced material models for steel as the "Multi-Linear Elastic-Plastic" model and the "Isotropic Hardening" model [9], both are used in the analysis. These models provide more sophisticated representations of steel behavior, incorporating features such as strain hardening, stress-strain hysteresis shown in Fig. 7, and cyclic loading effects.

Fig. 5. Hybrid constitutive material model of PVA-ECC [7].

Fig. 6. Developed constitutive Mander material model for concrete [8].

In nonlinear time history analysis, the direct integration process is employed to solve the equations of motion [10,11] shown in Eq. (1).

$$M \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + C \frac{dx}{dt} + Kx = P(t) \tag{1}$$

In the above equation, M denotes the structural mass matrix, C for structural damping, K indicates the structural stiffness matrix, $\frac{d^2x}{dt^2}$ is acceleration, $\frac{dx}{dt}$ denotes the velocity, and $P(t)$ defines the time-dependent loads. This process numerically integrates the equations of motion over time, step by step, to determine the response of the structure at each time increment. It incorporates nonlinear material behavior, geometric nonlinearity (p-delta), and damping effects, providing a comprehensive assessment of the structural response. The SAP2000 analysis program is utilized to define the ideal force-deformation relationship for the plastic hinges [9], as depicted in Fig. 8. Once the energy value of F_y is reached at point B, the structural member yields. Beyond point B, the applied force on the hinge varies with deformation. When the displacement reaches point C, the plastic hinge undergoes collapse. Eventually, the plastic hinge loses its capacity entirely, and when it reaches points D and E, the failure of the building is defined. An example of the locations of plastic hinges assigned within 10% of the end part of structural members is presented in Fig. 9.

Fig. 7. Elastoplastic constitutive steel material model [9].

Fig. 8. Idealized force-deformation relationship [9].

The determination of damage situations and performance levels of the buildings involves comparing the plastic-rotation values with the limit values specified in ASCE 41-13 [12]. Performance levels are categorized into three levels, similar to codes: immediate occupancy (IO), life safety (LS), and collapse prevention (CP). At the IO level, non-structural members may exhibit small cracks, but no damage occurs to the structural members. The LS level allows for limited damages while ensuring life safety while maintaining the lateral stiffness and rigidity of all structural members. The CP level involves the possibility of wall collapse and permanent displacements but aims to prevent total collapse describes the Fig. 10.

Fig. 9. Locations of plastic hinges.

Fig. 10. Structural performance levels [11].

To consider the P-delta effect in nonlinear analysis, an iterative process is employed. The analysis starts with assuming an initial geometry and computing the internal forces based on this assumption. Then, the

deformed shape is updated, considering the initial internal forces and the resulting deformation. The process is repeated until convergence is achieved, with the deformed shape and internal forces satisfying equilibrium. This research study adopts a conservative approach by considering a fully fixed or restrained support condition for the superstructure's foundation in the absence of considering any specific soil case or type. In this analysis, the focus is on worst-case scenarios, where the foundation is assumed to be completely rigid and immovable, disregarding the potential flexibility and interaction with different soil conditions. This approach aims to provide a conservative estimation of the structural response under seismic loads, ensuring a higher level of safety and reliability in the analysis. To determine the periods, the predominant modes of vibration are considered, and a 5% viscous proportional damping is applied. El Centro ground motion full data is used as a time history function.

3 Results and Discussions

Deformation, strain, ductility, and damage parameters are considered more reliable indicators than stress values for characterizing structures. The results presented in Fig. 11 showcase deformation, energy dissipation, and damage levels at representative critical joints of the frame system. Additionally, Fig. 12 illustrates the input energy (IE), which encompasses total kinetic, potential, modal damping, link damper, and link hysteretic energies. The analyzed structural modal periods vary by 0.21~1.62 seconds for twelve several modes and the predominant first modal period is 1.62 seconds.

Fig. 11. Critical Joints of RC and ECC Structures.

Fig. 12. Input energy of three buildings.

Furthermore, the displacements, including peak displacements, of the nonlinear semi-rigid frame joints highlight the superior performance of PVA-ECC structures compared to traditional RC structures. The displacement responses at representative joints are observed in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14.

(a) Displacement response of J1 at corner grid.

(b) Displacement response of J99 at corner grid.

(c) Displacement response of J179 at corner grid.

(d) Displacement response of J1 at corner grid.

(e) Displacement response of J99 at corner grid.

(f) Displacement response of J179 at corner grid.

Fig. 13. Displacement responses of the 12-story building of both RC and ECC at corner grid in critical joints.

ECC structures exhibit better survival rates in terms of internal work done and permanent deformation, particularly when using only 0.4% steel, which is three times less than RC structures. While joint J179 shows a different outcome due to its specific location, the overall sum of internal work done aligns with the other results. Additionally, the displacement responses of the remaining three joints in the middle grid line are depicted in Fig. 14.

(a) Displacement response of J2 at the middle grid.

(b) Displacement response of J100 at the middle grid.

(c) Displacement response of J180 at the middle grid.

(d) Displacement response of J2 at the middle grid

Fig. 14. Displacement responses of the 12-story building of both RC and ECC at the middle grid in critical joints.

Once again, the displacements, including peak displacements, of the semi-rigid joints in the nonlinear frame highlight the performance disparity between PVA-ECC structures and traditional RC structures. When considering a mere 0.4% steel reinforcement, which is three times less than that used in RC structures, ECC structures exhibit superior resilience in terms of internal work done and permanent deformation. Fig. 15 showcases the identical patterns of nonlinear hinge formations, providing visual evidence of the scenario.

Fig. 15. The plastic deformation in the inelastic stage is identified through performance levels.

In the case of RC soft floors with axial members experiencing differential displacement and increased vulnerability to sudden collapse during earthquakes. In contrast, the PVA-ECC building's soft story demonstrates high ductility, contributing to overall structural resilience.

4 Summary

Based on the findings from three buildings, a key factor contributing to the vulnerability of earthquake-resistant structures is soft floor irregularities that result in severe damage. Through nonlinear time history analysis of multistoried buildings, the study provides insights into the survival capabilities of PVA-ECC structures compared to conventional ones, taking into consideration the economic perspective. To enhance this study, further analysis of different structure types is recommended, employing the shake table test and quasi-static test in the laboratories. This would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of seismic resilience and facilitate the development of effective strategies for enhancing structural performance to choose the PVA-ECC structures as an alternative to conventional RC structures. The findings

contribute to the knowledge base for engineers and researchers in Bangladesh, guiding the design and implementation of ECC-based high-rise structures in earthquake-prone regions. Further research is recommended to explore additional aspects of PVA fibered ECC, such as long-term durability and constructability, to ensure its successful application in high-rise construction.

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